

Progress Report and Research Plan

Jeffrey M. Ede

j.m.ede@warwick.ac.uk

1 Progress

arXiv:1905.13667 Abstract: We present a multi-scale conditional generative adversarial network that completes 512×512 scanning transmission electron micrographs from partial scans. This allows electron beam exposure and scan time to be reduced by $20 \times$ with a 2.6% intensity error. Our network is trained end-to-end on partial scans created from a new dataset of 16227 scanning transmission electron micrographs. High performance is achieved with adaptive learning rate clipping of outlier losses and an auxiliary trainer network. Source code and links to our new dataset and trained network have been made publicly available at <https://github.com/Jeffrey-Ede/partial-STEM>.

arXiv:1906.09060 Abstract: Artificial neural network training with stochastic gradient descent can be destabilized by “bad batches” with high losses. This is often problematic for training with small batch sizes, high order loss functions or unstably high learning rates. To stabilize learning, we have developed adaptive learning rate clipping (ALRC) to limit backpropagated losses to a number of standard deviations above their running means. ALRC is designed to complement existing learning algorithms: Our algorithm is computationally inexpensive, can be applied to any loss function or batch size, is robust to hyperparameter choices and does not affect backpropagated gradient distributions. Experiments with CIFAR-10 supersampling show that ALRC decreases errors for unstable mean quartic error training while stable mean squared error training is unaffected. We also show that ALRC decreases unstable mean squared errors for partial scanning transmission electron micrograph completion. Our source code is publicly available at <https://github.com/Jeffrey-Ede/ALRC>.

arXiv:1910.10467 Abstract: Compressed sensing can increase resolution, and decrease electron dose and scan time of electron microscope point-scan systems with minimal information loss. Building on a history of successful deep learning applications in compressed sensing, we have developed a two-stage multiscale generative adversarial network to supersample scanning transmission electron micrographs with point-scan coverage reduced to $1/16$, $1/25$, ..., $1/100$ px. We propose a novel non-adversarial learning policy to train a unified generator for multiple coverages and introduce an auxiliary network to homogenize prioritization of training data with varied signal-to-noise ratios. This achieves root mean square errors of 3.23% and 4.54% at $1/16$ px and $1/100$ px coverage, respectively; within 1% of errors for networks trained for each coverage individually. Detailed error distributions are presented for unified and individual coverage generators, including errors per output pixel. In addition, we present a one-stage baseline network for a single coverage and investigate numerical precision for web serving. Source code, training data, and pretrained models are publicly available at <https://github.com/Jeffrey-Ede/DLSS-STEM>.

Wavefunction Reconstruction We have demonstrated that neural networks can reconstruct the phases of exit wavefunctions from their amplitudes if the distribution of possible wavefunctions is restricted. As a result, we are drafting a paper while we repeat successful experiments with more training iterations to achieve higher performance.

Datasets: We have set up a publicly accessible server to make some of our machine learning datasets publicly available <https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/sci/physics/research/condensedmatt/microscopy/research/machinelearning/>. Additional datasets have been uploaded and will be made available alongside associated publications.

Year 1: Projects completed in the first year of my PhD are detailed in my 2018 progress report; available at <https://www.overleaf.com/read/cqvxxkttshp>.

2 Research Plan

Research projects we are working on at the moment include

AI-LACBED: After a successful grant application for supercomputer time, we have simulated over 10000 large angle convergent beam electron diffraction (LACBED) patterns. Once simulations finish, we plan to train a neural network we have drafted/tested to accelerate LACBED by multiple orders of magnitude. We also aim to train a network we have drafted/tested to generate projected potentials from LACBED patterns.

Reinforcement Learning: We have invented an approach to address one of the limitations of reinforcement learning. We are in the process of implementing supporting architecture. This description is deliberately vague to avoid compromising the algorithm.

Adaptive Partial-STEM: Building on the spiral scans of partial-STEM, we have been developing an intelligent scan system that can dynamically adjust an electron beam path based on micrograph content. Learning is slow as the neural network makes tens of (asynchronous) CPU-bound callbacks to a simulation for each training example. As a result, we're considering CPU; rather than GPU-accelerated, training.

DLSS-STEM: We are packaging DLSS-STEM and have implemented the algorithm on an atomic resolution scanning transmission electron microscope. Once we have finished testing, we hope to make refinements based on user feedback.

Super-Compression: A compression/encryption algorithm we developed; initially for electron microscopy, has passed a prior art search and Warwick Ventures has approved a patent. As a result, we will refine and package the process in the next 1-2 years.

Webserver: We have been developing a neural network webserver so scientists in the electron microscopy group can run neural networks without local hardware acceleration or software dependencies. Once we resolve an issue with a websocket protocol to reduce latency, we intend to make our webserver internally available.

Thesis Writing: My PhD supervisor, Richard Beanland, has already been asked for feedback on a PhD thesis outline. I have prepared six papers (including papers affected by patent filing) for publication in the next few months that I can include in a thesis. As a result, I expect thesis writing to be focused on an introduction.

3 Other

I have completed the following MPAGS modules:

- PX904: Properties and Characterisation of Materials (2 credits)
- PX905: Defects and Dopants (2 credits)
- CH978: Surfaces, Interfaces and Coatings (2 credits)